

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARticle Data (SPEARHEAD)

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Deliverable 6.2 SPEARHEAD GitHub repository

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List of Acronyms

D	Deliverable
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
FDAT	Forbush Decrease Analysis Tool
ForbMod	Forbush decrease model for flux ropes
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
Geant4	GEometry ANd Tracking 4
G4VM	Geant4 Virtual Machine
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HET	High Energy Telescope
ICME	Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection
PR	Pull Request
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
TO	Technical Objective
VDA	Velocity dispersion analysis
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a report on the GitHub presence for the tools of the SPECification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data ([SPEARHEAD](#)) project. In this report, the overall layout of the GitHub representation of the project is presented. Furthermore, it describes in a generic way how individual tools are provided through independent repositories and how they are structured, from installation instructions to user contributions.

1 Introduction

The **SPEARHEAD** project aims to answer three main Science Questions (**SQs**):

- **SQ1: How are ions and electrons accelerated to the highest energies in solar eruptions, beyond 100 MeV/n and 1 MeV, respectively?**
- **SQ2: What are the processes governing particle release** from acceleration sites in the solar corona?
- **SQ3: What are the key processes of high-energy particle transport** in the interplanetary medium, in the magnetosphere and in the atmosphere?

In order to achieve these goals, three main Technical Objectives (**TOs**) of the project are proposed:

- **TO1: to develop and distribute analysis tools** to extract high-energy particle fluxes from particle detectors designed to operate at lower energies or to yield monitoring data. Response functions of spacecraft instruments will be determined and particle fluxes of the very high energy particles as a function of time and energy will be delivered.
- **TO2: to process and cross-calibrate a large number of data to produce high-energy particle flux datasets** and distribute them to the community.
- **TO3: to validate the data against intermittent direct spectrometer observations.**

This report on the **SPEARHEAD** GitHub repository gives a general description of the GitHub facilities that will be used to collaboratively work on the public tools that are part of **TO1** (following the **SPEARHEAD** Tools and Data Development Plan, Deliverable (D) 6.1; [Gieseler et al. 2024](#)) of the project and to provide them to the scientific community. For this, first the overall layout is presented, followed by a general description of the structure and processes of independent repositories containing the individual tools.

Note that the titular term “**SPEARHEAD** GitHub repository” may be a bit misleading. This is rather the overarching “**SPEARHEAD** GitHub organization”, which itself contains individual repositories for the independent tools.

2 SPEARHEAD GitHub repository

GitHub is a developer platform that allows developers to create, store, manage, and share their code. It uses Git software¹, which provides distributed version control of access control, bug tracking, software feature requests, task management, continuous integration, and optional wikis and discussion boards for every project.

SPEARHEAD utilizes GitHub for collaborative development and distribution of tools that are provided publicly under the “**SPEARHEAD** GitHub organization”. The scientific community can navigate through the repositories, get information about and download the tools, as well as provide feedback or participate in the future development through GitHub.

2.1 General structure

The general structure of **SPEARHEAD** tools developed and distributed through GitHub is the following. Each independent tool is located in an individual repository, and all these repositories are part of the overarching GitHub organization `spearhead-he`². This provides a central landing point for all the projects’

¹<https://git-scm.com>

²<https://github.com/spearhead-he/>

efforts at GitHub, which are not necessarily restricted to tool development, but can also be used, for example, to provide materials or tutorials for workshops or teaching courses, as the project progresses.

The screenshot shows the GitHub organization page for SPEARHEAD. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Overview', 'Repositories 4', 'Projects', 'Packages', 'Teams', 'People 7', 'Insights', and 'Settings'. The organization profile includes the SPEARHEAD logo, name, and description: 'SPECification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data'. It also shows 5 followers and social media links.

The main content area features a README file titled 'SPEARHEAD'. The README text describes the project as an EU-funded project for analyzing high-energy particle observations. It lists three science questions:

- How are protons accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions?
- What are the release times and spectral characteristics of near-relativistic particles from solar eruptions?
- How do coronal and interplanetary structures affect the transport processes of very high energetic particles?

 It also lists three technical objectives:

- Determining the response functions of a large number of spacecraft instruments to derive high-energy particle fluxes from observations at unprecedented accuracy releasing revised and completely new datasets
- Performing cross-calibration of datasets measured by science-grade and monitoring instruments to enable the use of monitoring data for scientific analyses
- Combining high-energy particle and context observations together with modeling of plasma structures for easier in-depth analysis of solar eruptions, quantifying their effect and delivering them to the community

 A disclaimer at the bottom states that the project is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101135044.

On the right side, there are sections for 'View as: Public', 'Discussions', 'People', 'Top languages' (Makefile, Jupyter Notebook), and 'Most used topics' (heliophysics, spacephysics, spaceweather).

The 'Pinned' section shows a repository named 'VDA' (Velocity Dispersion Analysis of Solar Energetic Particle events) which is a Jupyter Notebook.

The 'Repositories' section lists:

- .github** (Public): Updated 18 hours ago.
- VDA** (Public): Velocity Dispersion Analysis (VDA) of Solar Energetic Particle events. Includes a Jupyter Notebook, updated 19 hours ago.
- bowtie** (Private): Updated 2 days ago.
- G4VM** (Private): Includes a Makefile, updated 2 weeks ago.

Figure 1: The landing page of the SPEARHEAD GitHub organization.

Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the [SPEARHEAD](#) GitHub organization. The project's website and other dissemination channels are displayed at the top of the page for users to explore. The individual tools developed for the project are listed in the "Repositories" section and tab, with featured tools pinned to the top. General information for each repository such as the programming language, license, known/reported issues, etc. are also visible for each repository.

2.2 Individual repositories

Each independent tool resides in an individual repository that has as its landing page a README file providing, among others, information about the purpose of the tool and instructions on installation and usage. Figures 2 and 3 present a screenshot of one of [SPEARHEAD](#)'s tool repositories, the [VDA](#) (Velocity Dispersion Analysis) tool (see Sect. 2.3.4). First, a brief introduction on the purpose of the tool and other important information like its status are given, followed by step-by-step instructions on how to install and start it. Afterward, a short text describes how it is intended to be used, although most of the tools provided as Jupyter Notebooks will also include this and more information in the Notebook itself. Next, possible community contributions to the tool are covered. User engagement and also feedback within the team can take place in the issues section of each tool repository, where bugs or requests can be proposed and discussed, as shown in Fig. 4. Users from outside the project can also contribute to the software by forking the repository, adding code changes to their version, and opening a Pull Request (PR), which then needs to be approved by a team member after review. This is also the process by which code changes should be submitted from inside the project, and the principal developer responsible for each tool then reviews those changes in the corresponding PR.

After unit tests have been established for each Python tool, corresponding GitHub Actions are created that run these tests automatically on virtual machines in the cloud on every commit or PR, ensuring that code updates do not break existing functionality. Figure 6 shows an example of a successful passing GitHub Action in a PR for the bow-tie analysis tool (see Sect. 2.3.1). The status (passing or failing) of the last executed Python test GitHub Action is also indicated by a badge at the top of the corresponding repository's README, together with the percentage of the code covered by testing.

At the end of the page, the acknowledgments are given. Furthermore, for each tool repository, GitHub functionalities are used to quickly display the corresponding license, code of conduct, and release version in the sidebar (cf. Fig. 2 right). For each new release version published at GitHub, a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is automatically created at Zenodo. In addition, a copy of the repository at this stage is saved at Zenodo's server, where citations in common formats are also provided for each linked release version (see Fig. 5). The latest connected DOI is provided as a badge at the top of the repository's README, as shown in Fig. 2.

In the upcoming *JupyterHub for [SPEARHEAD](#) Tools* (D6.3, month 18), the repositories of tools based on Jupyter Notebooks will be automatically cloned to the JupyterHub server, and corresponding Python environments will be created from the provided requirement information. This results in a configuration, where a user directly after logging in to the JupyterHub server will find all the Jupyter Notebook tools pre-installed with all required software, so that they can directly start using them.

2.3 First set of SPEARHEAD tools

In this section, a quick overview is given on the first set of [SPEARHEAD](#) tools that are made publicly available together with this report at the end of 2024, which will be further developed openly on GitHub.

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository page for 'spearhead-he / VDA'. The repository is public and has 0 stars and 0 forks. The main branch is 'main' with 1 branch and 1 tag. The repository contains several files and folders, including 'examples', 'particle_data', '.gitignore', 'LICENSE', 'README.md', 'code_of_conduct.md', 'requirements.txt', 'vda_tool.ipynb', and 'vda_tool_configuration.py'. The README file is open, showing the title 'SPEARHEAD VDA tool' and a DOI of 10.5281/zenodo.14441054. The README includes sections for 'About' and 'How to install', with the latter providing a 6-step installation guide. The repository also has a code of conduct and a BSD-3-Clause license. The contributors list includes 'jgieseler' and 'liadlow'. A progress bar shows the repository is 95.5% Jupyter Notebook and 4.5% Python.

Figure 2: Example tool repository (Part A)

How to install

1. This tool requires a recent Python (≥ 3.10) installation. [Following SunPy's approach, we recommend installing Python via miniforge \(click for instructions\)](#).
2. [Download this file](#) and extract to a folder of your choice (or clone the repository <https://github.com/spearhead-he/VDA> if you know how to use `git`).
3. Open a terminal or the miniforge prompt and move to the directory where the code is.
4. *(Optional, but recommended)* Create a new virtual environment (e.g., `conda create --name vda`, or `python -m venv venv_vda_tool` if you don't use miniforge/conda) and activate it (e.g., `conda activate vda`, or `source venv_vda_tool/bin/activate` if you don't use miniforge/conda).
5. Install the Python dependencies from the `requirements.txt` file with `pip install -r requirements.txt`
6. Open the Jupyter Notebook by running `jupyter-lab vda_tool.ipynb`

How to use

The Notebook is separated into three main sections:

- Imports & Setup
- User Inputs
- Run

The user should run the cell(s) of the first section and then follow the instructions inside the Notebook to properly fill the input forms. The cells of the "Run" section can then be run without changing anything.

Contributing

Contributions to this tool are very much welcome and encouraged! Contributions can take the form of [issues](#) to report bugs and request new features or [pull requests](#) to submit new code.

If you don't have a GitHub account, you can [sign-up for free here](#), or you can also reach out to us with feedback by sending an email to jan.gieseler@utu.fi.

Acknowledgement

This tool is developed within the SPEARHEAD (*SP*Ecification, *A*nalysis & *R*e-calibration of *H*igh Energy *p*Article *D*ata) project. SPEARHEAD has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101135044.

The tool reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Figure 3: Example tool repository (Part B)

2.3.1 Bow-tie analysis

This Jupyter Notebook tool runs a bow-tie analysis ([Van Allen et al. 1974](#)) for the energy channels of a generic particle instrument, providing the user geometric factors (including errors) for and the effective energy of each channel. It can be obtained from <https://github.com/spearhead-he/bowtie>.

2.3.2 Forbush decrease analysis

The Forbush Decrease Analysis Tool (**FDAT**) is available at <https://github.com/spearhead-he/FDAT>. It is a Graphical User Interface (**GUI**) tool for analyzing Forbush decreases and Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection (**ICME**) events, conducting best-fit calculations of the Forbush decrease model for flux ropes (**ForbMod**, [Dumbović et al. 2018](#)) on selected data regions and performing in-situ analysis of

The screenshot shows a GitHub issue page for the repository 'spearhead-he / VDA'. The issue title is 'Update workflow to define the time window #3', which is currently closed. The issue was opened by 'jgieseler' 19 hours ago and has one comment. The comment from 'jgieseler' (Member) states: 'I think it would be helpful to improve the workflow to define the time window by two steps: 1. Provide an option to define the time window inside the Notebook (without csv file). Though providing it via csv file might be really helpful, in cases where the user only wants to investigate one event, it just complicates things. In addition, providing this file in a future JupyterLab environment will be troublesome. 2. Provide a working example. In case of the csv file, there should be an example file. The whole initial Notebook should be run without crashing if the user just executes all cells.' The issue is assigned to 'liadlow' and has labels 'documentation' and 'enhancement'. The issue was solved in commit 'aac6eca' and closed as 'completed' 14 hours ago. The right sidebar shows settings for assignees, labels, projects, milestones, development, and notifications. At the bottom, there is a comment input field and a 'Comment' button.

Figure 4: Example GitHub issue

ICMEs. Figure 7 shows examples screenshots from the start view (left) of the tool and an intermediate time-series plot of plasma data (right).

2.3.3 Geant4 virtual machine

The Geant4 Virtual Machine (G4VM), available at <https://github.com/spearhead-he/G4VM>, aims to make the new Geant4 simulations of the Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN) onboard Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) and Chandra as well as the High Energy Telescope (HET) onboard Solar Orbiter developed in Work Package (WP) 2 readily accessible (see Fig. 8 for a screenshot). The G4VM contains the corresponding Geometry Description Markup Language (GDML) models along

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Published December 13, 2024 | Version v0.1.0-alpha

spearhead-he/VDA: 0.1.0-alpha

Jan Gieseler · George Vasalos

Show affiliations

What's Changed

- This is the initial pre-release version 0.1.0

Full Changelog: <https://github.com/spearhead-he/VDA/commits/v0.1.0-alpha>

Files

spearhead-he/VDA-v0.1.0-alpha.zip

spearhead-he/VDA-v0.1.0-alpha.zip

- spearhead-he-VDA-de55a87
 - .gitignore 204 Bytes
 - LICENSE 1.5 kB
 - README.md 3.4 kB
 - code_of_conduct.md 3.4 kB
 - examples
 - datetime_range_example.csv 155 Bytes
 - reference_times_example.csv 86 Bytes
 - particle_data
 - .gitignore 0 Bytes
 - requirements.txt 260 Bytes
 - vda_tool.ipynb 61.1 kB
 - vda_tool_configuration.py 2.8 kB

Files (18.2 kB)

Name	Size	Download all
spearhead-he/VDA-v0.1.0-alpha.zip <small>md5:fa2e828654bcb314faa21b73127e23</small>	18.2 kB	Preview Download

1

VIEWS

0

DOWNLOADS

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Versions

Version v0.1.0-alpha	Dec 13, 2024
<small>10.5281/zenodo.14441054</small>	

Cite all versions? You can cite all versions by using the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14441053. This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one. [Read more.](#)

External resources

Archived in

[Software Heritage](#)
swh:1.dir:04e75776a463f14e6a6414688...

Available in

[spearhead-he/VDA](#)
Release: v0.1.0-alpha

Indexed in

[OpenAIRE](#)

Details

DOI

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14441054

Resource type
Software

Publisher
Zenodo

Rights

BSD 3-Clause "New" or "Revised" License

Citation

Jan Gieseler, & George Vasalos. (2024). spearhead-he/VDA: 0.1.0-alpha (v0.1.0-alpha). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14441054>

Style APA

Export

JSON
Export

Technical metadata

Created December 13, 2024
Modified December 13, 2024

Additional details

Related works

Is supplement to
Software: <https://github.com/spearhead-he/VDA/tree/v0.1.0-alpha> (URL)

▶ **Software**

Repository URL

<https://github.com/spearhead-he/VDA>

Citations

Show only:

Literature (0)
 Dataset (0)
 Software (0)
 Unknown (0)
 Citations To This Version

No citations found

Figure 5: Zenodo entry for a GitHub release version

The screenshot shows a GitHub Pull Request (PR) titled "Add GitHub Actions workflow for testing with pytest #1" in the repository "spearhead-he / bowtie". The PR is merged and shows a list of 6 commits, a comment from "jgieseler" stating "This introduces tests for all functions used in the Jupyter Notebook file.", and a "6 checks passed" section with 6 successful "build" checks. The right sidebar shows settings for reviewers, assignees, labels, projects, milestones, development, and notifications.

Figure 6: GitHub PR for the bow-tie analysis tool that includes indication of successful passing Python code testing by GitHub Actions.

with a compatible GEometry AND Tracking 4 (**Geant4**) application. The models incorporate the sensitive detectors of the instruments and the passive material shielding the detectors, represented with high precision. Each instrument is provided individually and with a spacecraft model that maps the spacecraft's shielding material onto spherical shell segments with varying densities to account for directionality. The **Geant4** application can be built independently but is provided in a configuration that works seamlessly within the recommended setup (for more details, see [Köberle et al. 2024](#)).

2.3.4 Velocity dispersion analysis

The **VDA** tool, available at <https://github.com/spearhead-he/VDA>, helps in the automation of the Velocity dispersion analysis (**VDA**) of one or multiple Solar Energetic Particle (**SEP**) events ([Vainio et al. 2013](#)). Each event is provided to the tool as a point in time. The user can parameterize the given Notebook and control which particle species are used, the sensor from which they are detected, and the viewings to be considered. The tool will then automatically obtain the necessary observations online and perform the analysis, providing the user in the end with a typical **VDA** plot as shown in Fig. 9. Plotted as onset times per inverse beta are the different energy channels of the chosen instrument. This is accompanied by a linear regression fit that provides the release time at the Sun and the path length the particles have traveled from there to the detector.

Figure 7: Start window of the FDAT tool (left) and a time series plot (right).

Figure 8: SOHO/EPHIN simulation within the G4VM

3 Conclusions and outlook

This report describes the [SPEARHEAD](#) GitHub presence, which serves as a platform for collaborative development and distribution of its public tools. The [SPEARHEAD](#) organization on GitHub hosts individual repositories for each tool, providing a central location for users to access, download, and contribute to the tools. Each repository features a README file that outlines the tool's purpose, installation instructions, and usage guidelines. Users can engage with the project by reporting issues, suggesting features, or

Figure 9: Example output of the VDA tool.

contributing code through Pull Requests (PRs). Each new release of a tool on GitHub is linked to a version-specific DOI for citation and archival at Zenodo. Throughout the ongoing project, additional tools are expected to be made available in the SPEARHEAD organization on GitHub, and the already available ones will be further developed. The upcoming JupyterHub SPEARHEAD server will allow users to easily access the Jupyter Notebook tools in a pre-configured environment.

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